

SECTION OF EARTH SCIENCES

HUMAN METEOROTROPIC REACTIONS IN RESPONSE TO SLIGHT FLUCTUATIONS IN ATMOSPHERIC PRESSURE

Gorgo Yu.

*Professor Department of Bioenergy, Bioinformatics and Ecobiotechnology
Igor Sikorsky National Technical University of Ukraine, Kyiv*

Abstract

The amplitude of low-frequency atmospheric pressure fluctuations was monitored, and the diurnal and seasonal dynamics of the APF were investigated, along with their correlations with other meteorological parameters. Correlations were also identified between the physical parameters of the APF and the frequency of emergency transport cases for cardiovascular diseases, sports injuries and suicide-related injuries during the monitoring period. It was established that the amplitudes of atmospheric pressure fluctuations have safe, risky, unfavourable and favourable ranges of influence on the frequency of emergency transport cases during APF with periods of 3–120 s. A comparison was also made of the influence of APF during periods of 120–1200 s on human meteorotropic reactions.

Keywords: weather; atmospheric pressure fluctuations; meteorotropic reactions; emergency transport events.

INTRODUCTION

Weather forecast is very important for the prevention of negative effects of weather factors on people health. According to numerous medico-meteorological studies the main significant meteorotropic parameters are air temperature, humidity, barometric pressure and wind velocity. Weather services provide the reliable information on these classical meteorological parameters on different time-scales all over the world. However, very little attention is paid to the effects on people of other non-classical meteorological parameters.

Recently, meteorotropic properties have been attributed to the slight atmospheric pressure fluctuations (APF) with second, minute and decaminute periods, related to the far-infrasound ($0.003 \text{ Hz} < f < 1 \text{ Hz}$) and internal gravity waves (from one minute and more) ranges [1-3]. Such APF are considered as natural noise in the atmosphere, originating from very different source. The most widespread and strong source of APF is chaotic turbulent noise of airflows [4,5].

The possible adverse effects of high levels of APF on human psycho-physiological, autonomic and vestibular functions were suggested by experimental studies with artificial oscillations of barometric pressure in the far infrasound frequency range. The paper [6] reports on autonomic and vestibular disorders in a group of subjects exposed to barometric pressure oscillations in special chamber (from 0.4 mm Hg (~50 Pa) to 4 mmHg (~500 Pa) with period characteristics of the far infrasound range (about 4 s)). The data presented the increase in number of mistakes during attention task performance, as well the deterioration of stato-kinetic ability. The changes in indices of mental activity, and autonomic reactions under extra-low-frequency pressure oscillations, modeling natural characteristics of APF, were observed in a group of subjects [7].

It have been suggested that heightened anxiety levels in people with mental disorders, as well the increase in incidence of suicides and occurrences of cardiac arrhythmias during episodes of strong wind could be at least partly due to biological response to ultra-

low-frequency pressure fluctuations created by wind induced turbulence [6,8,9]

Our experimental studies with animals, as well as studies of other authors in otolaryngology, suggest that special baroreceptors of APF exist in human body [10]. We found the biomechanical reactions of a certain part of the tympanic membrane (pars flaccida) in response to slight oscillations of air pressure in the far infrasound frequency range in the middle ear. The obtained data point out that the pars flaccida is capable of tracing the natural levels of APF, at least, from a few Pa and may be even from fractions of a Pa up to hundreds of Pa. Some studies suggest that there is a pathway, through which changes in the pressure are transmitted from the middle ear to the inner ear otolithic receptors [11,12], which in their turn mediate the vestibulo-sympathetic reflex [13]. Clinical observations suggested that high levels of APF had adverse effects on patients with rheumatic, cerebro- and cardiovascular diseases, as well disorders in the central nervous system [14]. A correlation between strong natural infrasonic waves and automobile accidents, as well as schoolchildren behavioral demonstrations of being unwell has been shown [15].

The important feature of APF is that they penetrate buildings and therefore could be responsible for weather sensitivity symptoms indoors, as well as outdoors. The potential risk of APF for people health is aggravated by the fact, that people cannot feel them and standard methods and means for their measurements are not available.

METHODS OF ANALYSIS

Long-term monitoring of atmospheric pressure was conducted in Kyiv, and the diurnal and seasonal variations in atmospheric pressure, as well as their relationships with other meteorological parameters, were studied. Correlations were also identified between the physical parameters of the APF and the incidence of emergency transport due to cardiovascular diseases, sports injuries, and suicide-related injuries in Kyiv during the monitoring period.

Atmospheric pressure was monitored in Kyiv over the course of one year—from July 1, 2015, to June 30, 2016. The study was conducted outdoors using a microbarometer. For these we used high sensitive (1 Pa) microbarometer with high temporal resolution (measuring rate 2 Hz) and specially developed computer program for calculation and visualization of APF spectral parameters.

The value of atmospheric pressure was recorded every 0.5 s. A special computer program, developed by us, was used to calculate the average integral amplitude of APF over each hour of the day in two ranges of their periods: 3 s - 120 s (second-minute periods) and 120 s - 1200 s (minute-decaminute periods). The first range was selected taking into consideration the results of our previous experimental investigations of biological effects of atmospheric pressure oscillations with periods in the range of far infrasound [6,16]. We are not aware of any studies that support the hypothesis that natural AFTs with periods extending beyond the range of acoustic phenomena are capable of influencing the human body and behaviour. The second range of APF periods with prevailing minute and decaminute waves of non-acoustical origins was selected to verify these suggestions. According to identification of frequency ranges accepted in the physics of atmosphere, APF were related primarily to infrasonic phenomenon in the first range, and to internal gravity waves in the second range.

Three-hourly meteorological data (temperature, relative humidity, wind velocity and atmospheric pressure) were obtained from Kyiv Geophysical Observatory for the same 1-year period.

Daily number of emergency transport events on circulatory system diseases (EEC) by International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision (I00-99) and sport (EESP) and suicidal (EESU) injuries for the same year period were obtained from the Kyiv Station of emergency services and medicine of catastrophes.

The mean daily amplitude of APF in two frequency ranges identified above was used for the analysis of relation with EEC, EESP and EESU. We used the mean daily values of temperature, relative humidity, wind velocity and atmospheric pressure to analyze the possible role of these classical meteorological parameters as confounding factors. We controlled the season and day of week effects, and allowed for the annual trend in EE to control the effects of slow-time varying environmental factors. All public holidays were excluded from the data.

Polynomial approximation was used to assess visually the functional character of the relation of EEC, EESP and EESU to increase in value of APF amplitude. We applied regression models to compare groups [17] for exploring the relationships between emergency transport events and independent atmospheric variables.

As dependency of emergency transport events on atmospheric variables may be non linear, the non-parametric smoothing method was chosen. We used the Loess technique to eliminate the confounding variables pattern in the data of emergency transport events in a stepwise manner.

The atmospheric variables, as well the number of emergency transport events, except for the EEC, were not normally distributed. Therefore, respectively the non-parametric (Mann-Whitney U-test and Sherman rank correlation test) and parametric (Tukey HCD) estimation were applied. Statistical analysis was performed with Matlab 6.6 (Curve Fitting Toolbox), Statistica 6 and MS Excell.

RESULTS

During APF monitoring, daily graphs of atmospheric pressure variations were obtained. Fig. 1 shows the daily dynamics of the deviation of atmospheric pressure from the mean value and the APF in two ranges of their periods: from 120 s to 1200 s and from 3 s to 120 s for two different days (the upper and lower parts of the fig.1).

Fig. 1 The daily dynamics of atmospheric pressure deviation from the average value and APF with periods: from 120 s to 1200 s (related mainly to non acoustical phenomenon – internal gravity waves) from 3 s to 120 s (related mainly to far infrasound phenomenon) for two different days. High APF amplitude levels were recorded at different times of the day on different days (upper and lower parts of fig. 1).

It should be noted that the annual average daily variation in the 1-hour average integral amplitude of the APF exhibited a distinct wave-like pattern in the first

and second frequency ranges (Fig. 2). However, the average range of the APF varies between the autumn–winter and spring–summer seasons.

Fig. 2 Daily variations in the average integral amplitude of atmospheric pressure fluctuations (APF) with periods ranging from 120 s to 1200 s and from 3 s to 120 s over a one-hour period during different seasons, averaged over the year.

The amplitude of APF was increasing in the first semi-wave from night to day, followed by a decrease in the other semi-wave from day to night. This shape was similar to such of classical meteorological parameters as temperature, wind velocity and inverse to relative humidity.

The year dynamics of APF amplitude revealed pronounced correlation:

- with wind velocity: for APF with periods 3 s – 120 s - $r = 0.72$,

for APF with periods 120 s - 1200 s - $r = 0.49$, $p < 0.00001$;

-with temperature: : for APF with periods 3 s – 120 s - $r = -0.38$,

for APF with periods 120 s - 1200 s - $r = -0.27$, $p < 0.00001$.

We also tested the relations between physical parameters of APF and rate of emergency transport events due to circulation systems diseases, sport and suicide injuries. Unfavorable for people health were high mean

daily values of APF in the far infrasound range (3 s – 120 s), as well the high ratio of the APF values during the nighttime to those during the daytime. We found non-linear relation between all selected kinds of emergency transport events and amplitude of APF in the far

infrasound range (AI) (Fig. 3). The number of emergency transport events increased significantly at the boundary between two categories of values of the APF amplitude: their high and middle-low values, pointing to threshold effects of APF.

Fig. 3 Daily number of emergency transport events coded as sport injuries (*EESP*), suicidal injuries (*EESU*) and circulatory system diseases (*EEC*) plotted against the number of days of the year, sorting by increase in mean daily integral amplitude of atmospheric pressure fluctuations with periods 3 s – 120 s (AI) and 120 s - 1200 s (AG)

We did not find the adverse effects on people with health problems of the APF in the range of longer periods (120 s – 1200 s). The number of EEC and EESP was significantly greater for days with high APF amplitude in this frequency range versus the days with low and middle levels of such APF. The threshold of APF levels for the increase in EESU was lower than those for the EEC and EESP, suggesting greater sensitivity of people with suicidal tendency to this atmospheric factor (tabl. 1). This is discussed in more detail in table 1.

Table 1 presents the values of the confidence intervals (CI: - 95% - + 95%) for: safety and risky range of amplitude of atmospheric pressure fluctuations (APF) with periods: 3 s – 120 s (AI) (related mainly to the far infrasound phenomenon); unfavorable and favorable range of amplitude of APF with periods, as well as for the unfavorable and favorable APF amplitude ranges with periods of 120 s to 1200 s (AG) (associated primarily with internal gravitational waves).

Table 1.

Safe and risky ranges of atmospheric pressure fluctuation amplitude (APF) with different periods.

N	Data	(CI: - 95% - + 95%)	(CI: - 95% - + 95%)	P
<i>APF with periods 3 s – 120 s (AI)</i>				
Safety amplitudes of APF Risky amplitudes of APF				
	APF amplitude	1.8 – 2.0 (Pa)	5.1 – 5.9 (Pa)	
1	EEC number	358.0 – 365.6 (n ₁ = 260)	366.8 – 381.0 (n ₂ = 87)	p < 0,01
2	EESP number	4.1 - 4.6 (n ₁ = 254)	366.8 – 381.0 (n ₂ = 87)	p < 0,032
	APF amplitude	1.1– 1.2 (Pa)	3.2 – 3.6 (Pa)	
3	EESU number	2.4 – 3.1 (n ₁ = 85)	2.9 - 3.3 (n ₂ = 260)	p < 0,044
<i>APF with periods 120 s – 1200 s (AG)</i>				
Unfavorable amplitudes of APF Favorable amplitudes of APF				
	APF amplitude	1.7 – 1.8 (Pa)	3.2 - 3.6 (Pa)	
4	EESP number	4.4 – 4.9 (n ₁ = 214)	3.8 – 4.5 (n ₂ = 131)	p < 0,011

n₁,n₂ – number of days emergency transport cases for two ranges of AF amplitude;

P - significance of the difference in number of emergency transport events.

The daily numbers of emergency transport cases (n_1 , n_2) related to cardiovascular diseases (EEC), sports injuries (EESP) and suicide-related injuries (EESU) are also presented, adjusted for variables that may introduce bias, for two ranges of AF amplitude.

DISCUSSION

We did not find the adverse effects of high amplitudes of the APF in the range of periods attributed mostly to the internal gravity waves phenomenon (fig. 3). Moreover, the obtained results (table. 1) point that their high values could be considered as activating factor promoting successful adaptation to sport activity and decrease in number of sport injuries.

According to our findings, even middle levels of APF dominating in common atmospheric condition can aggravate psychiatric disorders such as suicidal ideation. Unfavorable for the increase in EEC was also the low ratio of APF amplitude in the far infrasound range during the daytime to those during the nighttime.

The value of deviation of daily dynamics of APF in the far infrasound range from their normal daily shape towards increase in the nightly levels of APF relatively to their daily levels turn out to be the biologically important parameter. The obtained results suggest that low ratio of APF amplitude during the daytime to those during the nighttime (less than 1.5) can promote deterioration of ischaemic heart and hypertensive diseases. In contrast, the normal APF daily dynamics (with lower values at night and higher values during the day) seems to coincide with environmental characteristics promoting the circadian rhythm of circulatory physiological and biochemical processes. Particularly, such daily shape is demonstrated by autonomic shift from parasympathetic predominance at night to sympathetic prevailing drive in the day. Therefore, it can be speculated that decrease in APF amplitude at night and increase at day could cause domination of parasympathetic influences during sleeping and sympathetic influences during the day activity, promoting autonomic circadian rhythms. From this point of view the normal daily dynamics of APF can be considered as a beneficial environmental condition, especially for people with circadian disorders in circulatory functions.

Our previous experimental investigations of the effects of artificial atmospheric pressure oscillations in the far infrasound frequency ranges on mental, autonomic and biomechanical reactions, as well the present study suggest the important role of APF as a potentially risky meteorological factor for people health and environment safety, e.g. in traffic or at the workplace. From this point of view the systematic monitoring and forecasting of APF bioeffective physical parameters could be considered as actual task for weather services.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Studies into the effects of artificial fluctuations in atmospheric pressure within the far-infrasound frequency range on psychological, autonomic and biomechanical responses indicate that APF plays an important role as a potentially hazardous meteorological factor for human health and environmental safety, for example in road traffic or in the workplace.

2. The results of the study indicate that high-amplitude APF, predominantly in the far-infrasound frequency range, has a meteorological effect, acting as a

risk factor that contributes to the worsening of cardiovascular diseases and an increase in the incidence of sports injuries.

3. Continued monitoring of the physical parameters of the APF is of particular importance for gathering new data and advancing scientific research in the field of biomedical meteorology.

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